

Instructional Supervision and Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12491383>

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Abstract:

The duties of Master Teachers include providing teachers with technical support and oversight of their lessons. This study investigated the level of instructional supervision and technical assistance skills of Master Teachers in one of the medium-sized division in Southern Negros Occidental for the School Year 2023-2024. The study made use of descriptive research design, as well as a self-made questionnaire which was duly validated and reliability-tested. The respondents of the study are 49 Master Teachers distributed in 9 districts of the said SDO. The statistical tools used were frequency count and percentage distribution, mean, and Mann-Whitney U Test. The results showed that instructional supervision ($M=3.68$, high level; $SD=0.2847$) and technical assistance ($M=3.84$, high level; $SD=0.2892$) skills of Master Teachers are both on high level. The study also found no significant difference in the level of MT's instructional skill but there was a significant difference in their technical assistance skills. The study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the level of instructional supervision of Master Teachers while on the other hand, there was a significant difference in the level of technical assistance skills of Master Teachers. To address the lowest mean scores, the study recommended the full utilization of DepEd's Basic Education Research Fund (BERF); Provide ICT Refresher Course for effective delivery of lessons, Implementation of Collaborative Learning and Conduct of regular community education class for adult learners.

Keywords: Master Teachers, instructional supervision, technical assistance skills, teachers performance.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The 1987 Philippine Constitution mandates the creation, maintenance, and advancement of an all-inclusive, adequate, and integrated educational system that satisfies the demands of the Filipino people. Given that this is a state policy, it was incumbent upon the federal government to underscore the significance of educators in guaranteeing that each and every Filipino national obtains an education of the highest caliber (Gestupa, 2023).

As required by the constitution, the government enacted Republic Act 4670 of 1966, popularly known as The Magna Carta for Public School Teachers, to improve and advance the social and economic status, working conditions, and career opportunities of public school teachers. Moreover, Executive Order No. 500, popularly known as the Master Teacher Scheme (MTS), was put into effect in March 1978 with the intention of training and educating professionals who possess outstanding leadership abilities in both managerial and instructional roles (Ojale, 2019).

As instructional leaders, Master Teachers (MTs) look for ways to support and encourage their colleagues as they carry out their duties to improve students' learning through coaching and mentoring (Daing, 2015). Another responsibility given to master instructors is providing technical assistance (TA) to teachers. It is any form of professional guidance, help, or support to help them perform their jobs more successfully. It is an interactive, step-by-step process that makes use of technologies, process consultants, specialized knowledge, and a goal-oriented methodology.

The traditional definition of teaching assistant (TA) involves supervising, monitoring, evaluating, directing, and instructing. However, the new paradigm emphasizes coaching, advising, and empowerment more than before (DepEd, 2016). Taking all of this into consideration, the researcher created this study to assess the participants' technical support and instructional supervision abilities of Master Teachers.

Current State of Knowledge

Instructional supervision is a component of school administration that primarily focuses on meeting the acceptable expectations of the educational system and serves as a tool for quality control in the educational system. Educators, regardless of experience level, require essential assistance in carrying out the educational plans. As the leaders of

the school, principals must, therefore, support teachers in their work and participate in the execution of instructional programs by supervising the activities that teachers carry out with the students (Suele, Ameh, and Egbai, 2015).

Academic leaders like Master Teachers have embraced the traditional educational practice of collaborative learning (CL) in order to bring new ideas to the way that instructional materials are delivered. To maximize their own and each other's learning, it can be characterized as a collection of instructional and learning practices that encourage student collaboration in small groups (two to five students). Teachers have attempted to incorporate various cooperative learning activities into their classroom instruction in an effort to accomplish this goal. Research also reveals that there are times when using CL in regular classroom instruction is insufficient. For instance, even if teachers assign students to various groups, they don't necessarily set up the dynamics of these groups to promote productive cooperation (Le, 2018).

The development and maintenance of teachers' competency falls under the purview of the department heads, master teachers, and school administrators. Among these are participating in action research, attending additional trainings, and insets. The head of the school also oversees the following aspects of instruction supervision: reviewing lesson plans, student notes, work schedules, teachers' punctuality, regular attendance, classroom observation, demonstration, conferences, workshops, microteaching, moderation of exam questions, and moderation of marking schemes, among other things. In order to complete these responsibilities, the department heads and head teachers of the school must be able to supervise the teachers and encourage them to use their talents when needed. This will allow for the eventual improvement of instruction and instructional procedures (Suele, Ameh, and Egbai, 2015).

It is therefore suggested that principals, acting as catalysts, facilitate the implementation of various sets of instructional activities geared toward an effective, viable, vibrant, and qualitative educational system that will improve the teaching-learning situation in the input-process-output framework. Without this, educational endeavors may be an exercise in futility. This is because instructional supervision is the leverage point for instructional improvement, teacher competence, and the efficiency of the educational system, while unsupervised instruction may mar the standard of education (Usman, 2016).

Instructional supervisors delegate tasks and clearly define the duties associated with completing them; they then hold signees accountable for accuracy and punctuality. For staff performance to stay current with changes and advancements, it is critical that it be continuously observed and evaluated. According to Kankam (2016), the rise of an information- and knowledge-based society has changed how people think about learning, and new ways of thinking about learning call for new ways of teaching that put the teacher's function as a facilitator of learning in jeopardy. Teachers need to engage in a variety of productive professional activities, either alone or in groups, using professional development strategies like study groups, peer-coaching, action research, mentoring, teaching portfolios, team teaching, and in-service training, in order to sustain ongoing professional development. A system for ongoing assessment of the institutions' operations, particularly those related to the teaching process, must be established for educational institutions to meet their objectives.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Two theories served as the foundation for this investigation: Robert J. House's (1974) Theory of Leadership; and Robert Katz's (1955) Three-Skill Theory. According to House (1974), school administrators, such as grasp Teachers, need to properly grasp the leadership style known as "supervision," which is the center of the Theory of Leadership. This ought to make it clear what steps subordinates need to do in order to improve their performance and level of job satisfaction. The technical talents of Master Teachers are explained by the Three-Katz's Skill Theory, which is primarily focused on technical support, academic leadership, and mentoring. Technical, interpersonal, and conceptual skills are the three key skill sets that academic leaders need to possess, according to Robert Katz (1955). He asserts that specific technical competencies are essential for leaders to have in order to maximize their managerial effectiveness. This explains how Master Teachers' technical abilities enable them to support teachers in gaining the necessary pedagogical competence through ongoing coaching, mentorship, and classroom observation. Master Teachers need to have a working knowledge of education in order to effectively utilize a wide variety of talents as leaders. Through ethnographic research conducted in many civilizations and circumstances, these writers emphasized the importance of performances in understanding human behavior. According to performance theory, each and every one of us acts in our society.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of instructional supervision and technical assistance skills of Master Teachers in relation to their performance in one of the medium-sized schools division in Southern Negros Occidental for the School Year 2023-2024. Furthermore, the study sought to determine the following: 1) the level of instructional supervision of Master Teachers in terms of: curriculum planning and assessment, instructional delivery and ideas sharing; 2) the level of technical assistance skills of Master Teachers in terms of Facilitating Community Relations, Professional Development and Enhancement of Learning Environment; 3) if there is a

significant difference in the level of Master Teachers' instructional supervision; and) if there is a significant difference in the level of Master Teachers' Technical Assistance Skills.

Methodology:

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design to determine the level of instructional supervision and technical assistance skills of Master Teachers. This study's descriptive design is appropriate since its goal was to identify prevailing conditions or relationships, held beliefs and attitudes, processes and effects, and emerging trends. The design is a scientific methodology that entails monitoring and characterizing a subject's behavior without exerting any kind of influence.

Respondents

The respondents were the 49 Master Teachers distributed in 9 clusters of a medium-sized division in Central Philippines for the school year 2022–2023. The paper made use of purposive sampling to determine the sample size.

Instruments

To determine the level of instructional supervision and technical assistance skills of Master Teachers in relation to their performance this study made use of a self-made data gathering instrument which was subjected to Validity (4.80 - excellent) and Reliability testing (0.743 for instructional supervision and 0.746 for technical assistance skills ; both interpreted as "acceptable"). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1 gathered the respondents' socio-economic information, such as age, highest educational attainment, length of service and the number of trainings, for the respondents' profile. Part 2 contained the questionnaire proper with 36 line items. There were 6 line items per area, in a total of 6 different areas from instructional supervision and technical assistance skills.

Procedure for Data Collection

After completing the Validity and Reliability tests for the instrument, the researcher sought permission to conduct the study from the Schools Division Superintendent. The approved letter was then distributed to the schools heads where target respondents are assigned. The printed copy of the data-gathering instrument was given to target respondents outside of school hours so as not to distract the Master Teachers and the schools from their normal routine. The respondents were given three to four days to fill out and return the instrument. Finally, the accomplished data-gathering instrument was encoded and tallied to the pre-formatted Excel file for an orderly tabulation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used descriptive analytical scheme to determine the the level of instructional supervision of Master Teachers in terms of: curriculum planning and assessment, instructional delivery and ideas sharing. Mean was used as its statistical tool.

Objective No. 2 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of technical assistance skills of Master Teachers in terms of Facilitating Community Relations, Professional Development and Enhancement of Learning Environment; Mean was used as statistical tool.

Objective No. 3 used comparative analytical scheme to determine the significant difference in the level of instructional supervision of Master Teachers when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables and the tool used is Mann-Whitney U Test.

Objective No. 4 used comparative analytical scheme to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of technical assistance skills of Master Teachers when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables and the tool used is Mann-Whitney U Test.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that no personal information that could compromise the identity of the respondents was stored on any device in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, particularly with regard to the researcher's and analyst's access to the data. All of the collected data was solely accessible to the researcher. As a result, participants were fully informed about the methods used throughout the research and were urged to sign a consent form in order to participate. Participants were also given the assurance that no one, including the public, would learn of the information they disclosed. Furthermore, all materials gathered were disposed of properly. Lastly,

participants will have the option to voluntarily withdraw from this research study at any time during its duration. A study report would guarantee anonymity.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the data, the analysis, and interpretation of the same to meet the objectives of the study as stated in the objectives. All of these were made possible by adhering to specific protocols that provided precise data and solutions for every objective.

Descriptive Analysis on the Level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' according to the Areas, Curriculum Planning and Assessment, Instructional Delivery, and Ideas Sharing

Table 1

Level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in terms of Curriculum Planning and Assessment

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Curriculum Planning and Assessment		
<i>As a Master Teacher, I ...</i>		
1. help develop a well-planned curriculum that aims to eliminate learning gaps.	3.76	High Level
2. work hard to ensure optimum coverage of all domains within the curriculum.	3.92	High Level
3. advocate continuity of learning between fields across various levels.	3.78	High Level
4. encourage teachers to conduct action and innovation research studies in school and correlate results with current learning problems.	3.18	Moderate Level
5. provide reference point for evaluating learners' progress.	3.27	Moderate Level
6. allow teachers to provide immediate feedback to students with emphasis on their strengths and weaknesses.	3.29	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.53	High Level

Item No. 2 which states "As a master teacher, I work hard to ensure optimum coverage of all domains within the curriculum" got the highest mean score of 3.92, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, Item no. 4 which states "As a master teacher, I encourage teachers' to conduct action and innovation research studies in school and correlate results with current learning problems" got the lowest mean score of 3.18, interpreted as moderate level. This suggests that some MTs might not prioritize conducting classroom-based research studies or other creative research projects. These kinds of unique exercises are good for both teachers and students. These new strategies aim to raise teachers' competency and skill levels as the new paradigm in education takes hold.

This conclusion was supported by Kankam (2016), who explained that the rise of the information- and knowledge-based society has caused a shift in how people view learning and that new methods of teaching call for new methods of learning, which put the teacher's role as a facilitator of learning in jeopardy. Teachers need to engage in a variety of productive professional activities, either alone or in groups, using professional development strategies like study groups, peer-coaching, action research, mentoring, teaching portfolios, team teaching, and in-service training, in order to sustain ongoing professional development. A system for ongoing assessment of the institutions' operations, particularly those related to the teaching process, must be established for educational institutions to meet their objectives.

Table 2

Level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in terms of Instructional Delivery

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Instructional Delivery		
<i>As a Master Teacher, I ...</i>		
1. opt for personalized learning solutions that best complement the unique learning preference of individual learners.	4.22	High Level
2. implement student-oriented approach tailored to students' needs.	4.00	High Level
3. cater to individual academic strengths through curriculum-aligned instructional methods.	3.57	High Level
4. encourage teachers to deliver instructions using a fusion of practices and strategies proven to work for students.	4.04	High Level
5. ensure usage of accurate and updated contents and appropriate strategies.	3.90	High Level
6. utilize technology resources in the delivery of lessons whenever necessary and applicable.	3.20	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.82	High Level

Item No. 1 which states "As a master teacher, I opt for personalized learning solutions that best complement the unique learning preference of individual learners" got the highest mean score of 4.22, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, Item no. 6 which states "As a master teacher, I utilize technology resources in the delivery of lessons whenever necessary and applicable" got the lowest mean score of 3.20, interpreted as moderate level. The table revealed that there are MTs who are less engaged in the utilization of ICT-based instructions as part of the newly cascaded mandate on instructional delivery.

The study of Namunga (2017), which examined the impact of instructional practice monitoring on teaching and learning in sub-county secondary schools in Bungoma County, concurred with this result. It showed a strong correlation between instructional approaches and supervision. As a result, it was determined that Bungoma County secondary schools' teaching and learning were greatly impacted by supervision of instructional procedures.

Table 3
Level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in Terms of Ideas Sharing

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Ideas Sharing		
<i>As a Master Teacher, I ...</i>		
1. share and encourage teachers' to test best practices in their own local school.	3.88	High Level
2. provide lectures and additional teaching inputs to teachers' using the FGD (per grade level).	3.47	Moderate Level
3. writes and shares teaching journals to help improve teachers' competence.	3.90	High Level
4. share teachers' concerns and issues and initiate collective resolution to it.	3.78	High Level
5. conducts Learning Action Cell (LAC) regularly for the regular sharing of ideas and concerns with teachers'.	3.98	High Level
6. promotes collaborative learning sessions among teachers'.	3.22	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.70	High Level

Item No. 5 which states "conducts Learning Action Cell (LAC) regularly for the regular sharing of ideas and concerns with teachers" got the highest mean score of 3.98, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, Item no. 6 which states "promotes collaborative learning sessions among teachers" got the lowest mean score of 3.22, interpreted as moderate level. Because it promotes deeper learning and encourages students to share ownership and responsibility for their education, collaborative learning is crucial. This finding suggests that certain MTs may not be as focused on encouraging collaborative learning in the classroom. Collaborative learning is the ideal method for teachers to share ideas with one another. Collaborative learning is an effective educational technique because it improves communication, critical thinking, and teamwork abilities.

A study by Chilenski et al. (2016) examined the effectiveness of a cooperative partnership between community prevention teams and technical help providers. Data from 14 community prevention teams participating in the PROSPER project were gathered over a period of four and a half years from prevention team members and technical assistance providers. The levels of collaboration in one phase of collaborative team functioning are correlated with features of internal team functioning in subsequent phases, according to Spearman correlation analysis using longitudinal data. The findings imply that when planning and carrying out technical assistance activities, community collaborative prevention work should take into account the collaborative nature of the relationship between the prevention community team and the technical assistance provider. It may also be crucial to regularly evaluate these dynamics in order to support high-quality implementation.

Descriptive Analysis on the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' according to the Areas, Facilitating Community Relations, Professional Development, and Enhancement of Learning Environment

Table 4
Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in Facilitating Community Relations

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Facilitating Community Relations		
<i>As a Master Teacher, I ...</i>		
1. conducts community seminars and workshops for the community.	3.29	Moderate Level
2. facilitate mutual school-community collaboration and support.	4.06	High Level
3. promotes and sustain school outreach programs to immediate communities.	3.96	High Level
4. take the lead in fostering partnership with internal and external	3.90	High Level

stakeholders.

5. support school efforts in providing free education to street or community children.	3.69	High Level
6. advocate and promote healthy parent-teachers' relationship.	3.78	High Level
Overall Mean	3.78	High Level

Item No. 2 which states "As a Master Teacher, I facilitate mutual school-community collaboration and support" got the highest mean score of 4.06, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, Item no. 1 which states "As a Master Teacher, I conduct community seminars and workshops for the community" got the lowest mean score of 3.29, interpreted as moderate level. This implies the fact that some MT's are less engaged in providing community support in the form of workshops and seminars. In order to promote collaboration between schools and the community, master teachers play a crucial role. Their knowledge fills the gap, guaranteeing that both organizations collaborate well to promote the development and evolution of students. Whether it's coordinating neighborhood activities, involving parents, or working with nearby organizations, MTs' influence goes well beyond the classroom.

The support a teacher needs to accomplish their work more successfully is known as technical aid. A few examples of technical assistance could be hiring a facilitator for a board retreat, going to workshops or training sessions on exclusiveness or resident-centered practices, or working with a consultant to develop a fundraising plan or a strategic plan for the organization, such as a school or community, or on marketing, volunteer management, financial management, or fundraising. All of these things encourage the acquisition of new informational skills that can aid in the improvement and transformation of a company, and they should involve the active participation of board members, employees, and/or constituents (Varona, 2017).

Table 5
Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in Professional Development

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Professional Development		
<i>As a Master Teacher, I ...</i>		
1. encourage teachers to pursue post graduate studies.	4.04	High Level
2. Constantly update teachers' knowledge and skills in light of new teaching skills and contents.	4.02	High Level
3. help in facilitating teachers' promotion by discussing with them the steps and processes.	3.45	Moderate Level
4. recommend to the school head teachers' who are ready and worthy of promotions.	4.16	High Level
5. encourage teachers to identify existing learning problems and help them develop action research with innovative approaches.	4.02	High Level
6. recommend sending of teachers' other trainings and workshops to improve teaching competencies.	4.18	High Level
Overall Mean	3.98	High Level

Item No. 6 which states "As a Master Teacher, I recommend sending of teachers' other trainings and workshops to improve teaching competencies" got the highest mean score of 4.18, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, Item No. 3 which states "As a Master Teacher, I help in facilitating teachers' promotion by discussing with them the steps and processes" got the lowest mean score of 3.45, interpreted as moderate level. While each teacher's journey is personal and different, having mentorship and ongoing support from MTs is extremely important. This finding suggests that certain MTs are not as interested in supporting instructors who want to advance in their careers. This may vary from situation to instance because occasionally, teachers have expressed a desire to solve their own problems without the help of MTs. In any case, MTs might help instructors advance their careers in different ways or in other areas where support is needed.

The responsibility of overseeing the teachers in their particular schools and ensuring that they fulfill their duties efficiently falls on the shoulders of head teachers and master teachers. Head teachers and master teachers have a plethora of supervisory approaches at their disposal to enhance teaching-learning and, in turn, have a positive impact on pupils. Therefore, in order to ensure instructional competence by supporting teachers' professional and academic growth, instructional leadership should focus on a number of areas, such as scheduling of teaching and learning activities, adhering to curriculum requirements and the qualifications of teaching staff, providing teaching and learning materials and equipment, and formulating rules and regulations governing the behavior of students and teachers (Wanjiku, 2018).

Table 6
Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers in the Enhancement of Learning Environment

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Enhancement of Learning Environment		
<i>As a Master Teacher, I ...</i>		
1. help organize the annual in-service trainings.	3.80	High Level
2. mentor other teachers' in content delivery and skills acquisition.	3.33	Moderate Level
3. conducts remedial classes for slow learners.	3.90	High Level
4. teach co-teachers' on how to effectively utilize differentiated instructions.	3.84	High Level
5. collaborate with other stakeholders to help maintain school safety and cleanliness.	3.78	High Level
6. provide coaching sessions to newly-hired teachers'.	3.88	High Level
Overall Mean	3.75	High Level

Item No. 6 which states "As a Master Teacher, I conduct remedial classes for slow learners" got the highest mean score of 3.90, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, Item No. 2 which states "As a Master Teacher, I mentor other teachers' in content delivery and skills acquisition" got the lowest mean score of 3.33, interpreted as moderate level.

This outcome defies the common belief that MTs serve as teachers' mentors in a variety of capacities. It is now required for master teachers to pursue leadership development. In the usual teacher-related and educational activities, the concept of master teacher leadership still struggles to take off.

There is a parallel finding by Nakpodia (2016) who claimed that in the modern era, instructional supervision focuses on improving the teaching-learning environment for the benefit of both teachers and students, assists in identifying teachers' strengths and weaknesses, and provides follow-up activities aimed at strengthening identified areas of teachers' weaknesses. Additionally, it gives teachers recognition and fosters a friendly work environment built on good human relations.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' according to the Areas, Curriculum Planning and Assessment, Instructional Delivery, and Ideas Sharing when grouped and compared according to the Variables, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Number of Trainings Attended

Table 7
Difference in the level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in the Area Curriculum Planning and Assessment when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	25.66	271.000	0.694	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	20	24.05				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	27.53	237.000	0.316		Not Significant
	Higher	30	23.40				
Length of Service	Shorter	29	25.66	271.000	0.694		Not Significant
	Longer	20	24.05				
Number of Trainings Attended	Few	27	25.56	282.000	0.759	Not Significant	
	Many	22	24.32				

Table 7 shows the results on the significant difference in the level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in the Area Curriculum Planning and Assessment when grouped and compared according to age obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 271.000 and the p-value of 0.694, interpreted as not significant. In terms of highest educational attainment, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 237.000 and p-value of 0.316, interpreted as not significant. In terms of length of service, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 271.000 and p-value of 0.694, interpreted as not significant. In terms of numbers of trainings attended, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 282.000 and p-value of 0.759, interpreted as not significant.

This result implies that age, highest educational attainment, length of service and number of trainings have no significant impact on MT's curriculum planning and assessment skills. This means that any program to be implemented relative to curriculum planning can be implemented without opposition between groups.

Table 8
Difference in the level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in the Area Instructional Delivery when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	24.43	273.500	0.733	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	20	25.83				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	24.58	277.000	0.867	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	30	25.27				
Length of Service	Shorter	29	24.43	273.500	0.733	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	20	25.83				
Number of Trainings Attended	Few	27	23.28	250.500	0.341	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	22	27.11				

Table 36 shows the results on the significant difference in the level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in the Area Instructional Delivery when grouped and compared according to age obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 273.500 and the p -value of 0.733, interpreted as not significant. In terms of highest educational attainment, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 277.000 and p -value of 0.867, interpreted as not significant. In terms of length of service, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 273.500 and p -value of 0.733, interpreted as not significant. In terms of numbers of trainings attended, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 250.500 and p -value of 0.341, interpreted as not significant.

This implies that the MT's share the same level of skills and opinion in terms of instructional delivery. This will be helpful in the implementation of any project on instructional delivery because there will no problem along the way in terms of opposition.

Table 9

Difference in the level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in the Area Ideas Sharing when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	23.48	246.000	0.362	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	20	27.20				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	29.08	207.500	0.106	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	30	22.42				
Length of Service	Shorter	29	23.48	246.000	0.362	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	20	27.20				
Number of Trainings Attended	Few	27	24.74	290.000	0.886	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	22	25.32				

Table 37 shows the results on the significant difference in the level of Instructional Supervision of Master Teachers' in the Area Instructional Delivery when grouped and compared according to age obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 246.000 and the p -value of 0.362, interpreted as not significant. In terms of highest educational attainment, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 207.500 and p -value of 0.106, interpreted as not significant. In terms of length of service, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 246.000 and p -value of 0.362, interpreted as not significant. In terms of numbers of trainings attended, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 290.000 and p -value of 0.886, interpreted as not significant.

This means that in terms of instructional delivery, MT's share the same level of skills and opinion. This situation will be helpful in the implementation of programs relative to pedagogical strategies.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' according to the Areas, Facilitating Community Relations, Professional Development, and Enhancement of Learning Environment when grouped according to the Variables, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Number of Trainings Attended

Table 10

Difference in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in the Area Facilitating Community Relations when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	31.21	110.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Older	20	16.00				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	27.79	232.000	0.268	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	30	23.23				
Length of Service	Shorter	29	31.21	110.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Longer	20	16.00				
Number of Trainings Attended	Few	27	30.98	135.500	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Many	22	17.66				

Table 10 shows the results on the significant difference in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in the Area Facilitating Community Relations when grouped and compared according to age obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 110.000 and the p -value of 0.000, interpreted as significant. In terms of length of service, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 110.000 and p -value of 0.000, interpreted as not significant. In terms of numbers of trainings attended, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 135.500 and p -value of 0.001, interpreted as significant.

In terms of highest educational attainment, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 232.000 and p -value of 0.268, interpreted as not significant. The result showed that length of service and number of trainings affect MT's abilities in facilitating community relations. To backtrack a little, the less tenured MT's and those who have lesser trainings presumably belong to the younger group. The results here showed that the less tenured and those with lesser trainings are more willing to conduct community activities. The difference in their willingness and desire could be age related as well.

Table 11

Difference in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in the Area Professional Development when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	24.48	275.000	0.756	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	20	25.75				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	19	23.45	255.500	0.538	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	30	25.98				
Length of Service	Shorter	29	24.48	275.000	0.756	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	20	25.75				
Number of Trainings Attended	Few	27	23.93	268.000	0.553	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	22	26.32				

Table 11 shows the results on the significant difference in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in the Area Professional Development when grouped and compared according to age obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 275.000 and the p -value of 0.756, interpreted as not significant. In terms of highest educational attainment, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 255.500 and p -value of 0.538, interpreted as not significant. In terms of length of service, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 275.000 and p -value of 0.756, interpreted as not significant. In terms of numbers of trainings attended, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 268.000 and p -value of 0.533, interpreted as "not significant". In terms of professional development, MT's share the same level of opinion and skills. This can be due to the fact that all of them are required to obtain units for CPD purposes each and additionally, professional developments are needed for promotional purposes.

Table 12

Difference in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in the Area Enhancement of Learning Environment when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	29	23.88	257.500	0.500	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	20	26.63				
Highest	Lower	19	25.58	274.000	0.818	0.05	Not Significant

Educational Attainment	Higher	30	24.63			
Length of Service	Shorter	29	23.88	257.500	0.500	Not Significant
	Longer	20	26.63			
Number of Trainings Attended	Few	27	23.48	256.000	0.401	Not Significant
	Many	22	26.86			

Table 11 shows the results on the significant difference in the Level of Technical Assistance Skills of Master Teachers' in the Area Enhancement of Learning Environment when grouped and compared according to age obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 275.000 and the p -value of 0.756, interpreted as not significant. In terms of highest educational attainment, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 255.500 and p -value of 0.538, interpreted as not significant. In terms of length of service, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 275.000 and p -value of 0.756, interpreted as not significant. In terms of numbers of trainings attended, obtained a Mann-Whitney U test of 268.000 and p -value of 0.533, interpreted as not significant.

Conclusion

The level of technical assistance skills of Master Teachers in terms of Facilitating Community Relations, Professional Development and Enhancement of Learning Environment are all on high level. The level of performance of Master Teachers for the school year 2022-2023 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables is on a "very satisfactory level". There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and the performance of Master Teachers. There is no significant difference in the level of MT' instructional skills which means that all of them are indeed uniformly committed towards supporting teachers' instructional skills, providing them with the needed guidance on how to perform well that sooner or later, these mentees might be mentors soon. There is a significant difference in the level of MT's technical assistance skills in the area of facilitating community relations when grouped according to age, length of service and number of trainings and the significant results are all age-related. The younger respondents are the same MTs who are less tenured with less number of trainings. They too are more energetic and dynamic which by any reason makes them more capable to actively help the community in the forms of seminars or workshops.

Acknowledgment

The completion of this study was made possible through the collaboration and encouragement of the following individuals: Dr. Lilybeth P. Eslabon, Dr. May P. Bautista, and Dr. Rey T. Eslabon . Thank you for your assistance.

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Bio-profile

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